

Maps for land cover, deforestation hotspots, and reforestation hotspots in the Chocó-Darien Global Ecoregion at 2002 and 2015

Ecosphere

Drivers of forest cover changes in the Chocó-Darien Global Ecoregion of South America

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D) The files Land_Cover_CGE_2002 and Land_Cover_CGE_2015 quantify the land covers in the Chocó Darien Global Ecoregion of South America at 2002 and 2015. These maps were created using time series of the cloud-free MODIS vegetation index products MOD13Q1 (Terra vegetation indices 16-Day L3 Global 250m) and high spatial resolution imagery (WorldView-2, Quick Bird, Ikonos and GeoEye-1). Random Forest was the algorithm used to build these maps. The validation of these maps resulted in a Kappa of 0.87 (Sd= 0.008).

The map codes for Land_Cover_CGE_2002 and Land_Cover_CGE_2015 are:

- 0) Forest
- 1) Secondary vegetation
- 2) Grassland
- 3) Crops
- 4) Palm plantation
- 5) Settlement
- 6) Water
- 8) Wetland.

II) The files DEFOrestation_hotspots_2002_15 and Reforestation_hotspots_2002_15 identify the areas where deforestation (DEFOrestation_hotspots_2002_15) and reforestation (Reforestation_hotspots_2002_15) transitions were spatially clustered (hotspots). The land cover maps of the Chocó-Darien Global Ecoregion at 2002 and 2015 (Land_Cover_CGE_2002 and Land_Cover_CGE_2015) and Local Moran's tests were used to identify the 3x3 pixel matrices where were located deforestation or deforestation hotspots.

The map codes for DEFOrestation_hotspots_2002_15 are:

- 0) No deforestation hotspot
- 1) Deforestation hotspot

The map codes for Reforestation_hotspots_2002_15 are:

- 0) No reforestation hotspot
- 1) Reforestation hotspot